

35 **1. Introduction**

36 The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a universal call to action to end poverty,
37 protect the planet, and ensure that all people enjoy peace and prosperity by 2030. Adopted
38 by all United Nations Member States in 2015, the SDGs are a collection of 17 interlinked
39 global goals designed to be a roadmap for realizing a more prosperous and sustainable
40 future for everyone (United Nations, 2015). These goals encompass a broad range of
41 social, economic, and environmental development issues, from health, education, and
42 gender equality to climate change, ocean conservation, and urban sustainability. Unlike
43 their predecessors, the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the SDGs are unique
44 for their inclusive approach, targeting not just developing countries but all countries, and
45 emphasizing the interconnectedness of global challenges (Sachs, 2012). The success of
46 the SDGs requires a collaborative effort across countries, sectors, and societies, making
47 them a pivotal framework for international development in the 21st century. From the
48 outset, given this global orientation and significance, scholars and practitioners alike are
49 delving into the various dimensions of the SDGs, scrutinizing their advancement,
50 obstacles, and strategies for accomplishment, highlighting the vital importance of
51 research and innovation in addressing complex worldwide challenges (Griggs et al.,
52 2013).

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54 Research has extensively addressed the topic of the Sustainable Development Goals
55 (SDGs) from diverse perspectives, where scientometrics plays a pivotal role in the
56 monitoring and evaluation not only of the various proposals but also of the engagement
57 and efforts that researchers, universities, and nations invest in the SDGs (Confraria et al.,
58 2024; Pizzi et al., 2020; Salvia et al., 2019; Sweileh, 2020). This approach allows for a
59 comprehensive understanding of how the global research workforce contributes to
60 achieving these goals. This plurality of research through the lens of scientometrics
61 encompasses areas of interest such as the interconnections between the SDGs (Fonseca
62 et al., 2020), their influence on university agendas (Sianes et al., 2022), and the main
63 topics of research (Rafols et al., 2021). Despite the proven utility of scientometrics and
64 its methods for these purposes, there remains a lack of approaches that are valuable in
65 specific contexts by integrating this variety of methods in a way that can be replicated by
66 institutions for decision-making. This gap underscores the need for a more nuanced

67 application of scientometric techniques to fully capture the impact of the SDGs on
68 research agendas and scientific policies (Ràfols, 2019).

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70 Building upon this critical insight, the objective of this work is to establish an initial
71 methodological framework that leverages scientometrics for the study of the SDGs,
72 aiming to enrich university policy-making processes with robust data-driven insights.
73 This novel framework, inspired by the transformative potential of the SDGs as
74 demonstrated by Romero Goyeneche et al. (2022), employs bibliometric and social
75 network analysis to not only illustrate scientific knowledge production's role in
76 implementing the SDGs but also to evaluate and manage scientific production, research
77 topics, actor involvement, and their relationships, as suggested by Cassi et al. (2017).
78 Intended to influence science, technology, and innovation policies—particularly those
79 aimed at transformative innovation—this approach offers a strategic tool for enhancing
80 decision-making processes within universities. It encourages a paradigm where
81 scientometric insights do more than just inform; they catalyse policies that resonate with
82 the SDGs' principles and goals, thus optimizing the contribution of academic institutions
83 to sustainable development and transforming the science, technology, and innovation
84 system of specific regions.

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86 The paper is structured as follows: Initially, we delve into "The case of the Region of
87 Murcia," providing a detailed backdrop against which our research is framed, highlighting
88 its unique characteristics and the rationale for its selection. This is followed by the
89 "Methodology" section, which is divided into two parts: data collection and the
90 methodological proposal, explaining the innovative approach we have adopted for
91 identifying and analysing scientific publications relevant to the SDGs. Next, the "Results"
92 section is presented in two sub-sections, "Overall analysis" and "SDG analysis," where
93 we dissect the findings from our methodology application, offering insights into the
94 research landscape of the Region of Murcia and its alignment with the SDGs. Finally, the
95 "Discussion" section synthesizes the implications of our findings, emphasizing their
96 relevance to policy-making, regional research capabilities, and the broader quest for
97 sustainable development.

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101 **1.1. The case of the Region of Murcia**

102 To demonstrate its true potential, this work applies its methodological framework to a
103 real-world case study, focusing on a specific location, the Region of Murcia. This region
104 is in the southeast of Spain, is one of the 17 autonomous communities in the country.
105 These communities have specific administrative and legislative competencies, granting
106 them a certain degree of independence in various areas, including education, health, and
107 cultural promotion. Particularly in the field of science and research, Murcia, like other
108 autonomous regions, can formulate its own strategies and policies while also aligning
109 with national objectives (Jefatura del Estado, 2022). Over the years, Murcia has leveraged
110 this autonomy to establish a unique scientific footprint. Since 1997, the region has been
111 diligently tracking its scientific, technological, and innovation metrics, spanning areas
112 like international collaboration, Research and Development (R&D) recruitment, patent
113 outputs, and societal research impacts¹ (Centro de Información y Documentación
114 Científica, 2001; Delgado López-Cózar et al., 2006; Cabezas Clavijo et al., 2009, 2012,
115 2013, 2014; Fundación Séneca, 2010, 2019, 2023).

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117 Under the guidance of the Seneca Foundation's Science and Technology Observatory
118 (Observatorio de Ciencia y Tecnología de la Fundación Séneca), this data has informed
119 Research & Development + innovation (R&D+i) policies in Murcia. Initiatives such as
120 the RITTS 4452 Strategy (Fundación Séneca, 2003) and consecutive Regional Science,
121 Technology, and Innovation Plans were developed based on this analysis. Presently, the
122 emphasis is on the Smart Specialisation Strategies, RIS3Mur (“Estrategia de
123 Investigación e Innovación para la Especialización Inteligente de la Región de Murcia,”
124 2014) and RIS4 (“Estrategia de Investigación e Innovación para la Especialización
125 Inteligente y Sostenible de la Región de Murcia 2021-2027,” 2020), for the period 2021-
126 2027. These strategies, giving priority to digital transformation, sustainability, and
127 innovation enhancement, are tailored to highlight Murcia's distinct strengths and
128 prospective growth sectors. Opportunities for R&D+i collaboration between the Spanish
129 State and the Autonomous Communities have been expanded through the Supplementary
130 R&D+i Plans. Co-financed with Next Generation EU funds, these plans foster territorial
131 synergies via research, innovation, and knowledge transfer networks in several scientific-
132 technical domains. In this context, the Murcia Region leads the Marine Sciences

¹ <https://fseneca.es/web/publicaciones/informes>

133 Supplementary R&D+i² Plan and contributes to the Agri-food Plan³, with key objectives
134 aligned with the SDGs, emphasizing ecosystem conservation, environmental
135 sustainability, and climate change mitigation.

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137 Across Europe, regions and cities are experimenting with and disseminating practices,
138 often engaging a broad spectrum of stakeholders and citizens, on optimal methods to
139 localize the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their policies and financial plans
140 (CoR-OECD Survey, 2019). The Region of Murcia has proactively set forth a Sustainable
141 Development Strategy (Gobierno de la Región de Murcia, 2022) and a 2030 Agenda
142 Implementation Plan where Murcia is among the Spanish regions that have kickstarted
143 all the axes of the 2030 Agenda essential for regional implementation. It has excelled in
144 governance and strategic advancements related to the 2030 Agenda and uses regional
145 legal standards to contribute to the SDGs. Notably, normative impact reports
146 accompanying legislative drafts now integrate the projected impact on the SDGs (Región
147 de Murcia. Consejería de Transparencia, Participación y Administración pública, 2020).

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149 Historical analyses of the science, technology, and innovation system in the Region of
150 Murcia have largely adhered to the traditional scheme revolving around bibliometric
151 indicators of scientific production. Methodologies from various European strategic
152 instruments, especially smart specialisation and innovation, have guided these
153 assessments (Fundación Séneca, 2003). This approach has supplied continuous insights
154 into primary indicators of regional research and innovation activity connected to scientific
155 outputs (Cabezas Clavijo et al., 2014). Additionally, these assessments have expanded to
156 include altmetric data at the institutional level, allowing for a broader evaluation of the
157 social impact of research conducted within Murcia, showcasing the region's commitment
158 to measuring research influence beyond traditional academic citations (Torres-Salinas et
159 al., 2013). While these evaluations have been comprehensive, they remain confined
160 within a specific scope, as indicated by the data sources employed⁴.

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162 As highlighted by the findings of the Steering Research and Innovation for Global Goals
163 project (Ciarli et al., 2022), the misalignment between science, technology, and

² <https://thinkinazul.es/>

³ <https://fseneca.es/agroalnext/>

⁴ <https://fseneca.es/impactoRRSSpublicaciones/>

164 innovation (STI) activities and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can
165 significantly hamper progress towards achieving these goals. Addressing this gap
166 necessitates an exploration of the intricate relationships between STI and the SDGs,
167 employing a suite of analytical tools from various disciplines. This cross-disciplinary
168 approach is essential for dissecting these relationships across different types of actors,
169 geographical areas, and time frames. Given the current shortfall in evaluative mechanisms
170 that leverage the SDGs' full potential, coupled with an urgent need for an in-depth
171 understanding of research domains within the Region of Murcia, our innovative
172 methodology aims to pinpoint micro-topics via scientific publications and map them onto
173 the SDGs. This technique, which generates a comprehensive thematic breakdown of
174 scientific contributions over time, not only enables comparative analysis within the
175 broader context of the European Union but also steers science and technology policies
176 towards augmenting their impact on the SDGs. This strategy underscores the imperative
177 for integrated frameworks that both illuminate and incentivize the alignment of research
178 and innovation ecosystems with global sustainability objectives (Martin, 2013; Schot and
179 Steinmueller, 2018), thereby contributing to a more coherent and targeted approach to
180 fostering sustainable development.

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182 **1.2. Objectives**

183 Our main objective is to propose a methodological framework to explore the research
184 contribution of a region to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In addition, to
185 demonstrate this potential and validate the reliability of this methodology, a case study is
186 conducted in the Region of Murcia (Spain). The specific objectives are detailed below:

- 187 1. To introduce a method for mapping the micro-research topics that a region
188 contributes to within a given SDG.
- 189 2. To test the method through a case study with the Region of Murcia (Spain),
190 mapping the main research topics within a specific SDG and the actors
191 contributing the most to it.
- 192 3. Compare the results with those of the European Union (EU-15) to showcase the
193 differences and highlight those specific research fronts of the Region of Murcia.

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198 **2. Methodology**

199 **2.1. Data**

200 The dataset obtained from Web of Science addresses the following query: indexes from
201 the main collection of Web of Science (SCI, SSCI, and AHCI), period from 2000-2022,
202 types being Article and Review, and location being the Region of Murcia and EU-15. In
203 total, 39,012 publications were retrieved for the Region of Murcia and 10,477,999 for the
204 EU-15 during that period. Of these, 31,904 publications from the Region of Murcia were
205 assigned to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a process facilitated using
206 InCites⁵. In recent years, major academic databases like Web of Science and Scopus have
207 incorporated the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as part of their
208 thematic classification systems. Our study uses the InCites Schema Scope, a systematic
209 framework designed specifically for mapping scientific publications directly to relevant
210 SDGs. This schema employs a category-to-category mapping system that connects each
211 SDG with associated Micro Citation Topics. Since its introduction in January 2022 and a
212 significant update in April 2024, the schema has enhanced the clustering algorithm to
213 improve the accuracy of publication assignments to Micro Citation Topics. A total of
214 1627 Micro Citation Topics have been assigned to various SDGs, with some topics
215 overlapping across multiple goals, leading to 1981 instances due to this duplication. For
216 instance, SDG 3 'Good Health and Well-being' has the most topics assigned, totalling
217 1153, highlighting its extensive research scope. In contrast, SDG 17 'Partnerships for the
218 Goals' has the fewest, with only 8 topics, indicating its more focused scope.

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220 Once we had classified the SDGs according to InCites, we proceeded to analyse the
221 microtopics. Next, the micro-level topic was determined for each publication, using the
222 classification developed by the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS)⁶.
223 This classification of micro-level topics is the foundation for the Micro Citation Topics
224 in InCites, though the latter is a derived and revised outcome⁷, thereby reducing the

⁵ InCites assigns Sustainable Development Goals to publications according to a mapping established with the classification scheme of the Micro Citation Topics. In this way, each topic is associated with an SDG, consequently assigning one or more of the first 16 Sustainable Development Goals to the publications. Source: <https://incites.help.clarivate.com/Content/Research-Areas/sustainable-development-goals.htm>

⁶ CWTS annually produces, as part of the Leiden Ranking, a thematic classification based on the citation network of all papers and reviews indexed in Web of Science. The 2023 version encompasses publications from 2000 to 2022. From this map, publications are grouped into clusters, with each of these representing a specific research theme termed a micro-level topic. Source: <https://www.leidenranking.com/information/fields>

⁷ <https://incites.help.clarivate.com/Content/Research-Areas/citation-topics.htm>

225 original 4215 topics to 2487. In our case, the use of the CWTS classification over that of
226 InCites is because this system provides a map of science of the micro-level topics, which
227 can be used to map the research fronts and boundaries of an entity. It is important to note
228 that due to the methods used, which are primarily based on the clustering of citation
229 networks, not all publications are assigned a micro-level topic or an SDG. However, these
230 instances are in the minority.

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232 **2.2. Methodological proposal**

233 In this study, we introduce a methodological proposal centred on a detailed mapping of
234 specific research fronts, which allows for the delineation of the particularities and primary
235 contributions of a region to research in general and in relation to the development of a
236 specific SDG. In this instance, the region under analysis is the Region of Murcia, with the
237 EU-15 serving as a broader framework representing the general trends of the scientific
238 system within which this region is situated. To materialise this approach, we implemented
239 an overlay map on the micro-level topics (Rafols et al., 2010), projecting the number of
240 publications each topic holds. By comparing the distribution of these topics between the
241 Region of Murcia and the broader European context, the overlay map acts as a visual tool
242 to pinpoint the specific research areas where the Region of Murcia and the EU-15 are
243 active. Such a comparison offers an immediate and intuitive understanding of the
244 disparities between them. This, in turn, allows for the identification of particular research
245 themes where the Region of Murcia makes a unique contribution compared to the general
246 European trend. Using scientific maps as a foundation, these differences are thoroughly
247 examined, not just in terms of raw numbers, but in the distribution and concentration of
248 topics. Extending this methodology to the SDGs further illuminates the specific research
249 areas wherein the Region of Murcia distinctly contributes to the advancement of a
250 particular SDG.

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252 However, when using the CWTS classification, we lack a precise and comprehensive
253 description of each micro-level topic, but rather a set of descriptors. Therefore, in order
254 to carry out a more useful analysis, a more detailed and complete description of the
255 research covered was assigned to each micro-level topic. This process was carried out
256 using ChatGPT (GPT-4). A prompt was developed in which our need to transform related
257 keywords into a specific research topic was specified. The entire methodological process
258 is summarised in Figure 1. Finally, we should point out the limitations in interpreting the

259 data. It is important to recognize that the SDGs function as a classification system. In this
260 unique context, their scientific accuracy may vary, and in no case do they directly reflect
261 a scientific contribution towards achieving the SDGs. However, the principal role of this
262 classification is to highlight a region's capability to conduct research on specific topics
263 that are part of the published agendas. As such, the SDGs operate similarly to any other
264 classification system.

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266 Supplementary material has been created that offers expanded and detailed views of
267 Figures 2 and 3 included in this article. These figures are available on Zenodo at the
268 following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/14524641>

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270 Figure 1. Summary of the methodological proposal

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273 3. Results

274 3.1. Overall analysis

275 To offer a contextual understanding of the Region of Murcia's research landscape, we
276 have drawn upon key bibliometric indicators. These metrics encompass the total number
277 of documents produced, the Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI), the proportion
278 of publications in top-tier (%Q1) journals, the percentage of international collaborations
279 (%Int. coll.), and the extent of open access (%OA) publications.

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281 Over the span from 2000 to 2022, Murcia's evolution in research output and influence is
 282 evident (Table 1). The region has witnessed sustained growth in its research contributions,
 283 increasing from 3,436 documents in the period 2000-2004 to 14,273 by 2018-2022.
 284 Moreover, the increase in the CNCI value to 1.15 in the latest period implies that the
 285 research originating from Murcia holds an influence that is above the global average. The
 286 nearly 10% increase in publications in journals ranked in the first quartile (Q1) of their
 287 respective Journal Citation Reports (JCR) categories reflects the improvement in research
 288 excellence within the region. Further, the surge in international collaborations from just
 289 over 23% to nearly 48% showcases Murcia's expanding research ties on the global stage.
 290 Coupled with a remarkable growth in open access publications, which has quadrupled in
 291 this period, these trends underscore the Region of Murcia's rising prominence and
 292 adaptability in the wider European and global research panorama.

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294 Table 1. Region-Murcia Bibliometrics indicators in three different periods

Time	Documents	CNCI	%Q1	%Int. coll.	%OA
Period 1 2000-2004	3436	1.00	41.66%	23.52%	15.98%
Period 2 2009-2013	8555	1.02	47.19%	34.28%	27.90%
Period 3 2018-2022	14,273	1.15	50.98%	47.72%	63.23%
Overall 2000-2022	39,012	1.09	48.51%	39.36%	41.89%

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296 When examining the distribution of micro-level topics between the EU-15 and the Region
 297 of Murcia (Table 2), notable differences and trends emerge. For the EU-15, the
 298 Biomedical and Health Sciences (BHS) dominate with 40.71% of publications (3,978,503
 299 publications), followed by the Physical Sciences and Engineering (PSE) at 25.69%
 300 (2,510,548 publications). The Region of Murcia, however, shows a higher percentage of
 301 publications in the BHS at 41.75% (15,755 publications), but a distinct drop in the PSE
 302 domain with only 12.60% (4,757 publications). Life and Earth Sciences (LES) in Murcia
 303 represent 25.63% (9,674 publications), a significant increase compared to the 15.20%
 304 (1,485,599 publications) seen in EU-15. Meanwhile, Mathematics and Computer Science

305 (MCS) and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) show less pronounced variations
 306 between the two regions.

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308 Table 2. Distribution of micro-level topics and publications from Europe (EU-15) and
 309 the region of Murcia by area

	EU-15				REGION OF MURCIA			
	Topics	%	Publ.	%	Topics	%	Publ.	%
SSH	479	11.36%	954,952	9.77%	310	11.19%	3508	9.29%
BHS	1343	31.86%	3,978,503	40.71%	1079	38.95%	15,755	41.75%
PSE	1131	26.83%	2,510,548	25.69%	556	20.07%	4757	12.60%
LES	530	12.57%	1,485,599	15.20%	414	14.95%	9674	25.63%
MCS	732	17.37%	842,050	8.62%	411	14.84%	4047	10.72%
Total	4215	100%	9,771,652	100%	2770	100%	37,741	100%

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311 This data underscores Murcia's pronounced emphasis on the Biomedical and Health
 312 Sciences and the Life and Earth Sciences, while it appears to place less focus on the
 313 Physical Sciences and Engineering when compared to the wider European landscape.
 314 However, this merely indicates whether the overarching research focus between the two
 315 systems is centred on the same areas; it does not necessarily suggest that Murcia's specific
 316 research topics align with European trends. This distinction becomes evident when
 317 contrasting the micro-level topic maps of the Region of Murcia with those of Europe
 318 (Figure 2). As observed, there are areas in Murcia with a notably reduced presence
 319 compared to Europe, such as research related to PSE. In Murcia, research is centred
 320 around 556 micro-level fields, compared to Europe's 1131, and publications in this
 321 domain account for 13% as opposed to Europe's 26%. Additionally, certain micro-level
 322 topics in Murcia display a marked dominance, allowing for the identification of specific
 323 research front that stand out in comparison to the broader European map.

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331 Figure 2. Micro-level topics map of the Region of Murcia and Europe (EU-15)

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334 Examining the table 3 reveals interesting contrasts between the Region of Murcia's
 335 research emphasis and the broader research distribution in Europe across various areas.

336 In the Social Sciences and Humanities, the prominence of "Sports Psychology" in Murcia
 337 is notable, representing 7.04% of the area's focus, a stark contrast to the 0.70% in Europe.

338 This trend of distinct focus continues across other fields. For instance, in Biomedical and
 339 Health Sciences, "Strength and Endurance Training" receives considerable attention in

340 Murcia at 3.41% compared to Europe's 0.39%. The same pattern is evident in Physical
 341 Sciences and Engineering, with "Electrochemical Processes" at 3.93% in Murcia versus

342 Europe's 0.13%. Additionally, in the realm of Mathematics and Computer Science,
 343 "Functional Analysis" in Murcia stands out at 4.84%, contrasting with Europe's 0.30%.

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350 Table 3. Main micro-level topics of the Region of Murcia by area

Area	Micro-level topic	EU15 %	Murcia %
Social Sciences and Humanities 479 micro-level topics	Sports Psychology	0,70%	7,04%
	Innovative Knowledge Management	1,49%	4,76%
	Corporate Finance and Governance	0,88%	2,71%
	Monetary and Fiscal Policies	1,64%	2,42%
	Childhood Psychological Disorders	0,97%	2,19%
Biomedical and health sciences 1343 micro-level topics	Strength and Endurance Training	0,39%	3,41%
	Fertility	0,21%	2,02%
	Eye Surgery	0,20%	1,47%
	Dental Implants	0,28%	1,34%
	Anticoagulant Therapies	0,24%	1,26%
Physical sciences and engineering 1131 micro-level topics	Electrochemical Processes	0,13%	3,93%
	Ionic Liquid Chemistry	0,34%	2,69%
	Conductive Polymers	0,16%	2,59%
	Palladium-Catalyzed Reactions	0,30%	2,35%
	Particle Physics	0,45%	2,08%
Life and earth sciences 530 micro-level topics	Plant Response to Salinity	0,48%	3,81%
	Food Preservation	0,13%	2,56%
	Soil Health Assessment	0,90%	2,50%
	Fruit Phytochemicals	0,57%	2,49%
	Aquatic Pathogens	0,27%	2,32%
Mathematics and computer science 732 micro-level topics	Functional Analysis	0,30%	4,84%
	Geometric Analysis	0,32%	4,47%
	Cluster Algebra	0,71%	3,19%
	Stochastic Analysis	0,25%	2,82%
	Dynamical Systems	0,58%	2,74%

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352 The highlighted differences between the Region of Murcia and the broader European
 353 context serve as a testament to Murcia's distinctive research trajectory. Such divergences
 354 can be attributed to a myriad of factors, from unique regional necessities and available
 355 resources to specialised expertise cultivated within the area. It becomes evident that
 356 Murcia has not only identified specific arenas of research where it can excel and create a
 357 niche but has also consciously or organically veered away from some of the predominant

358 European research trends. This deep dive into Murcia's research landscape provides
359 invaluable insights into the broader efforts and directions a specific region can adopt,
360 making it easy to pinpoint areas of specialisation and deviation from larger European
361 norms. It is worth noting that this overarching methodology, which sheds light on general
362 research trajectories, can be seamlessly applied to Sustainable Development Goals
363 (SDGs) to further elucidate how Murcia's contributions are aligned with these global
364 objectives and its particular contribution to them.

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366 **3.2. SDG analysis**

367 The table 4 elucidates how research publications related to the Sustainable Development
368 Goals (SDGs) are distributed between the Region of Murcia and the wider European
369 context. At a cursory glance, the numbers between Murcia and EU-15 seem broadly
370 aligned for several SDGs, especially for overarching goals such as "Good Health and
371 Well-Being", where both have approximately 60% of publications. Similarly, the
372 alignment is observable in "Gender Equality" and "Clean Water and Sanitation", both
373 registering close percentages. However, some distinctions are notable. For instance, the
374 "Zero Hunger" SDG shows a stark difference with Murcia attributing 7% of its
375 publications to this goal, as compared to the broader 3% seen in EU-15. Another area of
376 significant divergence is "Climate Action", with Murcia devoting 12% of its publications,
377 contrasting with the 10% in EU-15.

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391 Table 4. Distribution of publications in the Region of Murcia and Europe (EU-15) by
392 SDGs

SDG	EU-15	EU-15	Reg. Murcia	Reg. Murcia
1 No Poverty	101,994	1%	184	1%
2 Zero Hunger	260,813	3%	2340	7%
3 Good Health and Well-Being	4,817,643	59%	19,125	60%
4 Quality Education	193,963	2%	892	3%
5 Gender Equality	372,738	5%	1621	5%
6 Clean Water and Sanitation	234,428	3%	989	3%
7 Affordable and Clean Energy	374,619	5%	516	2%
8 Decent Work and Economic Growth	104,995	1%	299	1%
9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	223,243	3%	849	3%
10 Reduce Inequalities	131,558	2%	262	1%
11 Sustainable Cities and Communities	592,442	7%	1798	6%
12 Responsible Consumption and Production	177,809	2%	615	2%
13 Climate Action	841,400	10%	3722	12%
14 Life Below Water	237,871	3%	1321	4%
15 Life On Land	490,277	6%	2918	9%
16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions	59,068	1%	58	0%
Total	8,108,539	100%	31,904	100%

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395 It is crucial to understand that while these percentages might hint at an alignment or lack
396 thereof in the general focus, they do not necessarily imply that the underlying research
397 themes within each SDG are the same. Indeed, the nuances within each SDG can vary,
398 especially given that some variations between Murcia and EU-15, even if minimal, can
399 represent entirely different research orientations or priorities. This perspective and
400 potential of the proposed method become evident when focusing on a specific SDG, such
401 as SDG 13 (Climate Action).

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403 When comparing the micro-level topic maps of Murcia and Europe for SDG 13, the
404 interpretation becomes much more intuitive and apparent than in the general case (Figure
405 3). Firstly, it's much easier to discern which areas are generally engaged, with it being
406 evident from the European perspective that these largely encompass themes within Life

407 and Earth Sciences and Physical Sciences and Engineering. However, for Murcia, the
 408 core lies within Life and Earth Sciences, with noticeable absences in other areas.
 409 Secondly, it also becomes clear which micro-level topics receive the most focus and the
 410 differences between the two. For instance, "Plant Response to Salinity" (ID 28) has a
 411 significant presence in Murcia, whereas in Europe it's not even discernible.
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 413 Figure 3. Map of SDG 13 micro-level topics of the Region of Murcia and Europe (EU-
 414 15)

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 417 First and foremost, Murcia's research orientation in this area is distinctively unique (Table
 418 5). This is most evident in the topic "Plant response to salinity," which accounts for a
 419 considerable 9.91% of Murcia's publications, in contrast to just 0.83% in the broader EU-
 420 15. Similarly, "Soil health assessment" and "Diversity of bryophytes" are other major
 421 focal areas for Murcia, while their representation in EU-15's research landscape is
 422 relatively lower. Notably, some topics, like "Viticulture" and "Decoding of viral
 423 genomics," show a significant presence in Murcia's research output, suggesting a
 424 particular regional specialisation or interest. On the other hand, when observing EU-15's
 425 dominant topics related to SDG 13, areas such as "Petrogenesis and Geochronology" and

426 "Atmospheric Chemistry" prominently feature, yet their representation in Murcia's
 427 research is minimal. This stark contrast underscores the varied regional priorities and
 428 expertise.

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430 Table 5. Main SDG 13 micro-level topics of the Region of Murcia and Europe (EU-15)

Area	Micro-level topic	EU15 %	Murcia %	ID
Region of Murcia	Plant response to salinity	0,83%	9,91%	28
	Soil health assessment	1,42%	6,28%	13
	Diversity of bryophytes	0,28%	5,92%	2372
	Viticulture	0,51%	5,16%	1159
	Decoding of viral genomics	0,73%	3,96%	322
	Ecology of seagrass meadows	0,36%	2,35%	1739
	Ecology of field birds	1,42%	2,32%	51
	Combating plant invasions	0,83%	2,27%	373
	Paleoclimatic studies	2,03%	1,91%	57
	Prehistoric archaeology	0,91%	1,83%	696
EU-15	Petrogenesis and Geochronology	2,60%	0,05%	1
	Paleoclimatic studies	2,03%	1,91%	57
	Atmospheric Chemistry	1,99%	1,56%	6
	Monsoon Patterns	1,55%	1,34%	10
	Paleobiology and Paleoclimate	1,48%	0,14%	148
	Probing Solar Physics	1,44%	0,14%	63
	Marine Biogeochemistry	1,43%	0,22%	89
	Soil health assessment	1,42%	6,28%	13
	Ecology of field birds	1,42%	2,32%	51
	Volcanology	1,23%	0,03%	552

431

432 These disparities highlight Murcia's distinctive contribution to research related to SDG
 433 13. While some topics overlap, like "Ecology of field birds," Murcia's emphasis on certain
 434 areas diverges considerably from the broader European trends, evidencing its particular
 435 research interests and strengths in this sustainability domain.

436

437 **4. Discussion**

438 The methodology presented in this work represents a significant step forward in detecting
 439 research topics within a science policy context. While this study employs a specific
 440 geographical context (the Region of Murcia), a concrete comparative framework (the
 441 European Union), and a targeted classification (the Sustainable Development Goals), the
 442 approach itself is versatile and adaptable. The novelty of this methodology lies in the

443 combination of these elements rather than in the individual components, which are well-
444 established. By integrating bibliometric analysis, micro-topic mapping, and content
445 enrichment using tools such as ChatGPT, this methodology offers a nuanced
446 understanding of research contributions that can be extrapolated to other contexts.
447 Specifically, this perspective can be applied to various agents, including institutions,
448 research centres, or national scientific systems, and can be scaled to different
449 geographical frameworks, from individual regions to countries or even global analyses.
450 Moreover, the methodology is not limited to SDGs; it can be adapted to other thematic
451 classifications. This flexibility enhances its potential as a valuable tool for science policy,
452 supporting evidence-based decisions to align scientific efforts with broader societal and
453 policy objectives.

454

455 The methodology employed in the present work marks a new phase in this analysis, as it
456 considers the essential element of the SDGs in a scenario lacking proposals and evaluative
457 tools that harness their value and potential. This methodology identifies micro-topics in
458 scientific publications and maps them to the SDGs. This approach creates a micro-scale
459 map of productive research areas in the Region of Murcia, their volume, and the
460 responsible organizations. Simultaneously, it facilitates comparison with the results in the
461 European Union, assessing common elements and peculiarities, and enabling comparison.
462 In essence, this methodology captures the interdisciplinarity and thematic diversity of
463 scientific production at the regional level applied to a case study with a comprehensive
464 analysis of research topics in the Region of Murcia, allowing for a visualisation of a
465 thematic structure through its scientific production and highlighting strengths and
466 emerging lines, thus guiding scientific and technological policies to enhance their
467 contribution to the SDGs.

468

469 At Fundación Séneca, the entity responsible for promoting researcher training, talent
470 attraction, and scientific excellence in the Region of Murcia, we recognize the need for a
471 robust methodological framework to guide scientific policies. This study significantly
472 supports this objective, enabling strategic decisions aligned with the 2023 Program-
473 Contract, in collaboration with the Regional Ministry of Environment, Universities,
474 Research, and the Mar Menor. The study's results enhance decision-making in key areas
475 of regional science policy. The analysis identifies fields with scientific output below
476 European standards, facilitating targeted funding calls through "Regional Programs for

477 Scientific and Technical Research Excellence, Knowledge Transfer, Valorization, and
478 Scientific Entrepreneurship”. This approach directs resources toward addressing
479 deficiencies, fostering balanced growth in the regional R&D&I ecosystem.

480

481 Moreover, the study highlights areas of strength within the Region of Murcia, forming a
482 basis for policies aimed at expanding strategic fields. These insights have supported the
483 “Regional Program for Research Talent and Employability”, which attracts, retains, and
484 develops highly qualified human resources, ensuring sustainability and competitiveness
485 in priority sectors. The findings also inform the design of innovation strategies, such as
486 the RIS4Mur Plan (Research and Innovation Strategy for Smart & Sustainable
487 Specialisation of the Region of Murcia 2021-2027), ensuring alignment with regional
488 capacities and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Integrating these insights into
489 policy-making fosters evidence-based decisions, advancing the socio-economic
490 development of the Region of Murcia.

491

492 The results of applying this methodology prove highly valuable, not only for
493 understanding regional capacities in research and innovation, their projection, and their
494 peculiarities (often explained by the presence of institutions specialising in certain areas
495 such as biomedical or agri-food), their alignment with policies and instruments promoted
496 by the European Union, and their contribution to them, but also crucial for shaping the
497 Regional Strategy for Scientific and Technical Research and Innovation, currently under
498 development, for defining regional R&D+i policies and programmes, and for their
499 alignment with strategies and policies driven by the European Union and its funding
500 programmes.

501

502 The methodology introduced in this work, along with its application in the Region of
503 Murcia, offers an innovative approach to understanding and measuring progress toward
504 implementing the SDGs. By identifying the most scientifically productive areas and those
505 with high application potential, the methodology aligns research priorities with regional
506 social and economic needs. It supports the transformation of the research and innovation
507 system and informs the design of science, technology, and innovation policies. These
508 insights help orient activities toward the SDGs by enhancing scientific infrastructures,
509 fostering knowledge generation, attracting and developing research talent, promoting
510 knowledge transfer, and encouraging science-based innovation and entrepreneurship.

511 Furthermore, this approach contributes to building a culture of scientific and
512 technological engagement among citizens, ensuring that research and innovation efforts
513 address regional challenges and support sustainable development.

514

515 Organisations and actors in the regional system and regional STI policy makers can
516 benefit from this guidance to make better decisions on actions affecting the above aspects
517 and on the allocation of investments, improving the implementation of the SDGs and
518 extending their impact and transformative capacity in the multiple spheres of society they
519 reach. The elaboration of the Regional Science and Technology Strategy of the Region
520 of Murcia for the period 2024-2027 is linked in the organisation of the regional
521 government to a new Department that brings together the competences to elaborate and
522 execute policies in universities, research and environment.

523

524 In this context, the methodology and results of this work, and particularly the
525 methodology that allows to accurately map micro-topics in their thematic mapping to the
526 SDGs, constitute an unprecedented opportunity to inform the new orientation of the
527 Regional Strategy, which requires a new thematic agenda oriented towards sustainability,
528 preparing the policies to accompany it, providing a new approach to governance based
529 on reflexivity and building such governance with a focus on foresight, elements that have
530 been considered key to the success of European policies and programmes, in particular in
531 Horizon Europe: the EU framework programme for Research and Innovation (R&I)
532 2021-2027 (European Commission and Directorate-General for Research and Innovation,
533 2023), in its pursuit of the SDGs (Kastrinos and Weber, 2020).

534

535 The framework provided by this study will make it easier for regional policies to look at
536 European policies and programming instruments until 2027, including thematic
537 guidelines, lessons on governance and future prospects, taking into account that these
538 elements are explicitly and decisively referred to the SDGs of the 2030 Agenda of the
539 United Nations in these policies and programming, which will contribute to strengthening
540 the central role of transitions towards sustainability and social inclusion at regional level,
541 as a basis for their development. At the same time, thanks to the comparative capacity of
542 the methodological tool, it will allow to measure the contribution that the effort in science,
543 technology and innovation from the Region of Murcia can represent for the achievement
544 of these goals at a global level and, from a broader perspective, to show the capacity of

545 public policies and research and innovation activity at the local and regional level as key
546 elements of transformation.

547

548 **Acknowledgments**

549 The authors would like to thank the Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS)
550 for providing the data used in the thematic classification, which was obtained during the
551 research stay of Wenceslao Arroyo-Machado.

552

553 **Contributorship**

554 WAM – Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology,
555 Project administration, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft

556 AG – Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft

557 MTL – Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – original draft

558 DTS – Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology

559

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646

647

648 **Figure legends**

649 Figure 1. Summary of the methodological proposal

650

651 Figure 2. Micro-level topics map of the Region of Murcia and Europe (EU-15)

652 For an expanded view, see Figure S1 at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14524641>

653

654 Figure 3. Map of SDG 13 micro-level topics of the Region of Murcia and Europe (EU

655 15). For an expanded view, see Figure S2 at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14524641>